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Site Transportation Impact Analysis in Kaduna, Nigeria

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Abstract: Traffic congestion problems are increasing in Nigeria, significantly due to poor transportation planning, rapid urbanization, inadequate road development, and rapid population growth. Existing infrastructure is inefficient to cater for this, and dictates a need of precise transportation planning to overcome congestion and delays problems. This paper mainly explains the research undertaken to improve the traffic system of Kaduna, Nigeria, by formulating a comprehensive methodology that not only covers traffic and transportation impact analyses but also incorporates the environmental impacts for Nigeria. A successful project in Kaduna is taken and followed as a model project to formulate a Traffic impact analysis for Nigeria. The study included the procedures of conventional four-step travel demand modelling technique that are successfully proposed to Kaduna Nigeria. The research focuses on improving Nigeria's transportation system highlighting practical solutions for traffic congestion and environmental issues simultaneously. Furthermore, the proposed guidelines will facilitate transportation planners in Nigeria to develop congestion mitigatory measures and environment-friendly infrastructure development plans.

Keywords: Transportation Impact Analysis (TIA), Data collection for TIA, Traffic Survey Procedure, Urban Congestion Mitigations.

1. Introduction

With the urbanization on the rise worldwide, extensive land development has caused a massive increase in the inflow of people to the urban centres, leading to a rise in vehicle demands. This increase in demand stretched the capacity of the existing transport systems. The expansion of urban centres is unanimously dependant on the travel behaviour, demand, and supply of the concerned area. The deteriorating conditions of urban transport systems, especially in under-developed countries need immediate attention, for which the concept of travel demand management should get a major concern. Traffic congestion has been built up as the most overwhelming effect of land use transformation because of the adjustment in the limit of land use in Nigeria [8]. For handling travel demand, it is essential to plan a suitable transport system. To plan transportation facilities, it is necessary to forecast their performance, and alternatives should be implicated to the project [4].

Transportation impact analysis (TIA) is a powerful tool that coordinates traffic, land use and travel movement of individuals at the micro-level. TIA refers to the analysis or prediction of the impact on urban traffic, traffic safety, and traffic environment after the completion of the project, and later to plan corresponding improvement and modification schemes [9]. TIA helps in maintaining a certain level of service during the project development, and ensures the normal operation of the traffic system inside and outside the development site, and implementing countermeasures. The main objective of TIA is forecasting the impacts of construction of a project that affects the surrounding traffic facilities

significantly [9]. The major difference between transportation impact analysis and Traffic impact analysis is that transportation impact analysis incorporates all modes of transportation ranging from an individual-trip like walking and cycling to public transportation. At the same time, Traffic impact analysis only covers road traffic without incorporating the system of transit [9].

The essence and relevance of environment impact analysis (EIA) to sustainable development are significant. The EIA Act 1992 by the Nigerian government made the application of EIA mandatory on all major development projects in the country [15] it purposed is strictly on analysing the environmental level of a project. EIA is known as a method for economical advancement embraced by Nigerian legislation and planners to solve the environmental problems [8]. According to the Nigerian Constitution [16], "the state will protect and improve the environment and safeguard the water, air and land, forest and wildlife of Nigeria". But application of EIA is linked with various ambiguities in Nigeria, which are a challenge to its approach for analysing projects traffic [12]. However, these rules and regulations states that before any individual, corporate body, or organization chooses to embrace or approve the endeavour of any movement that may likely or altogether influence the environment, earlier thought of its ecological impacts should initially be taken, subsequently the requirement for the readiness of an EIA report [16]. According to [12], EIA has challenges in the form of relatively narrow spatial, less coordination between traffic and land use at the micro-level, limited use on projects (dams, transportation infrastructure, industrial plant [19], self-restricting, and incapable reaction to the current size of environmental decay [6]. On the other hand, TIA continues to analyze the project even after the completion and could be applied to all kinds of projects.

Nigeria is a developing country with a massive population. The population is ever-growing at a greater rate. For instance, Lagos is a major city in Nigeria, and its masses population is rapidly increasing quicker than the number of inhabitants in NYC and LA in America, and also more than the number of inhabitants in 32 African nations consolidated [1]. 85% of the total populace of Lagos is concentrated on a 37% area of the city, with no proficient travel framework. This development rate, in addition to the turbulent character of the urban vehicle framework, has shown mixed results. A portion of these incorporate long travel times out and about, helpless street condition to a great extent because of abuse and absence of support, a significant level of outflow and contamination from vehicles, despicable street framework, and traffic clogs along significant passageways of the state. Each project is a producer of traffic, and other project tasks is able to produce huge enough congestion to make blockage, prompting increasingly open interest in the transportation industry. Traffic blockage prompts monetary expenses because of travel delays, air and commotion contamination and mishaps. Street turns out will turn out to be increasingly blocked, drivers will, in general, go to other streets not intended for the particular use [5].

The research on TIA in Nigeria is very less [8]. In request to evaluate the exhibition of TIA in Nigeria, the comprehension of the rules is imperative to portray the usage of TIA in the nation [18]. This research will provide a guideline for the transportation planners in future to develop a comprehensive system for dealing with traffic congestion issues. The motivation behind this is to expand traffic congestion effects on current developments around the urban regions, on the case improvement, traffic conditions, and traffic control gadgets required to be influenced by expanded traffic volume.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Selection of Chinese TIA

TIA was introduced in China in the 1990s [21]. Over the preceding decade, the level of urbanization and motorization has improved rapidly, with the development of China's national economy [14]. To formalize the connection between land use and transportation, incorporated methodologies utilizing numerical, factual and consistent models are equipped for forecasting the progressions to transportation and land-use frameworks [7]. The population and rate of increase of GDP of China are immense. The normalized percentage of people owning a personal vehicle in China will be equivalent to that of Nigeria in future. The successful implementation of Chinese TIA in China to control traffic congestion has attracted author's interest to apply the same in Nigeria, The Technical Standard for Traffic Impact Evaluation of Construction Projects is now approved as the industry standard, No. CJJ/T141-2010, since 2010. This standard is published and distributed by China Construction Industry Press, organized by the Standard Quota Institute of the Ministry of China. [3] . The contents

of china's traffic impact analysis are explained in Figure 1. This has now become a national standard and is used throughout China.

Figure 1: Contents of the Chinese TIA

<p>1. Research Scope of Project</p>	<p>2. Project Background and current traffic survey</p>	<p>3. Traffic volume forecast by systematic analysis</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cannot be limited to project itself -Whole area should be examined for impact of project on surroundings and relationship between land use and transportation should be determined. -Transportation demand and supply to be balanced. -Scope should be extended for projects that require preliminary traffic impact analysis. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Background of the project site to be included. -Surrounding land use status and transportation system, and the future land use and transportation planning of the study area should be included. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Quantitative analysis of the relationship between various land use and development intensity and traffic volume production or attraction. - Prediction of traffic volume generated by the target year construction project. - Superposition effect of these traffic volumes and urban road network load.
<p>4. Traffic impact assessment</p>	<p>5. Improvement of traffic facilities</p>	<p>6. Conclusion and Recommendations</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Analyse supply and demand of transportation facilities in traffic impact study area and compare it with road network capacity. - Evaluate impact of construction project on the surrounding traffic environment, including the impact of the traffic generated by the construction project and evaluate and test the existing traffic planning schemes. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Proposal of improvement measures for reducing the impact of construction project on the surrounding environment, after the analysis and evaluation. -Handling the balance between internal and external traffic and proposing corresponding traffic improvement and management measures. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The key requirements are to indicate whether the scale of the project is appropriate, whether the improvement measures are effective, and the evaluation of the project layout.

2.2. Details of the selected site project

The commercial development is situated in Kaduna, Nigeria. Kaduna is situated at 10.52° North latitude, 7.44° East longitude with a total land area of 431 km² (166 sq mi) and 614 meters elevation above the sea level. Kaduna is a very large town in Nigeria, having about 9,582,102 people. The project site is located on WAFF Road, north Kaduna District, Kaduna city, Nigeria. The surrounding supporting facilities are being renovated, with convenient transportation and beautiful environment. To the West and East of the site are Mohammed Buhari Road and Alimi Road, leading to Independence Way Road, connecting the North-Central Ring Road. The main surrounding buildings include Murtala square golf club and polo, handle hotel, GT bank, and Independence way road in the west and Muhammad Buhari road in the south of the site are the main access roads for traffic in the future. The location of Kaduna and the proposed site is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Location of proposed site in Kaduna

The site covers a total gross area of 19000 square meters. The gross area in hectares is 1.9 hectare, with 150 motor vehicle parking spaces and 28 non-motor vehicle parking spaces. Figure 3(a) and 3(b) show the under-construction site and the planned project model, respectively.

Figure 3: Proposed site: (a) Under construction site; (b) Model after completion

2.3. Transportation survey of selected Project

The development level of the site is relatively high. After being put into use, the new pedestrian and vehicle traffic will have a certain impact on the road network around the site, especially on Mohammed Buhari Road, Sokoto Road and also Independence Road. If the traffic organization problems caused by the site development are not solved well in time, it will greatly affect the realization of the expected functions of the project. Also, the development scale of the project exceeds

the threshold value proposed by the traffic impact assessment of Kaduna Nigeria construction project. Therefore, it is necessary to analyse and evaluate the traffic volume generated and attracted by the site development and its impact on the road traffic around the site, to deepen, optimize and improve the existing planning and design scheme, coordinate the contradiction between the site development, construction, urban traffic and to support the realization of the site planning and design objectives. The traffic impact assessment scope of the construction project is determined according to the impact degree of the newly generated traffic demand of the construction project and the operation condition of the surrounding traffic system of the construction project during the assessment year. Every city or county has its own transportation impact study area threshold. There is no defined method for determining the scope of study in Nigeria, so, the Chinese scope of the study can be applied because of the similarities of greater population, large quantity of personal cars, and the rate of growth of GDP. Chinese roads are well developed and planned in a grid pattern to form a square around each residential or commercial block. In contrast, Nigerian roads lie at greater distances from each other in a haphazard pattern. To cater for this, China's national standard threshold is modified to fit the standard of Nigerian roads owing to the similarities in the population growth, and rate of urbanization the evaluation scope of TIA of the concerned construction project is determined according to the modified version as provided in Table 1.

Table 1: Traffic impact of construction project scope in Kaduna city

The ratio of construction project size index to startup threshold (R)	Traffic impact assessment scope
R < 2	The vicinity of the first secondary roads or main roads
2 ≤ R < 5	The range of natural enclosures such as adjacent main roads or expressways
R ≥ 5	The vicinity of the second main road or expressway

The threshold of TIA of the construction project in Kaduna is explained in Table 2. The building area and parking space index of the project exceeds the starting threshold of traffic impact assessment. Considering the various traffic impact degrees that may be generated by the project construction, scale and the ratio of the project scale index to the starting threshold ($r = 1.9 / 1 = 1.9$) are analysed. This paper conducts traffic impact assessment for the areas surrounded by Muhammad Buhari way Road, independence way Road, Alimi road and Racecourse road through improvement planning.

Table 2: Threshold of traffic impact assessment of Kaduna construction project

Location	Total floor area (5,000 square meters)	
	Commercial (T02), service (T03), office (T04) and other public construction	Residential (T01)
The central area of kaduna north District	≥1	≥2
the area outside the kaduna north area (kaduna south District)	Chapter II ≥2	Chapter III ≥3
Chapter IV All new projects with more than 100 parking spaces		
Construction of new stadiums and gardens (T05) and medical (T06) construction projects with more than 100 parking spaces		
School-based (T07) construction project		
Transportation hubs, large parking lots, road projects or rail transit projects that require closed roads (occupied roads) (T08)		
All industrial projects with a land area > 2 hectares (T09)		
Hybrid (T10) construction project, whose total construction area or index reaches the starting threshold of any of the categories of construction projects included in the project (T01~T09, T11)		
Non-traffic municipal engineering projects (T11) that are heavily constructed on expressways, trunk roads, and secondary roads, and which are considered to be in need of traffic impact assessment (T01~T11)		

The project is scheduled to start in December 2019, and the mall will be delivered in May 2021. According to the construction plan of the site, the decoration after mall handover, the process of putting the project into use, and the first year of normal use should be 2022. To sum up, the traffic

impact assessment period of the project is 2022. Table 3 shows the determination of the years of evaluation.

Table 3: Determining years of evaluation

The ratio of total construction area to starting threshold (R)	Traffic impact assessment scope
R < 5	Normal use in the early years
R ≥ 5	1. Normal use of the first year 2, the normal use of the fifth year

The current survey of the surrounding road facilities is presented in Table 4. Road and transportation planning is derived from Google maps. The travel demand is forecasted so that the need for future planning from the government is assisted in case there will be another road constructed before the project is completed.

Table 4: Current survey of surrounding road facilities

Roads and Streets	Type	Direction	Width	Cross section width	Division	Pedestrian way	Shoulder width	Green Area and median
Md. Buhari way Road	Secondary	West-east	23.3 m	3.65 m each	Two-way two-lane	1.3 m	1.4 m	2.6 m -
Independence way	Main	North-south	26.5	3.65 m each	Two-way two-lane	1.7 m	-	- 5 m
Alimi Road	Small	East-west	13.6	3.5 m each	undivided	1.8 m	1.0 m	- -
Racecourse Road	Secondary	South-north	17.8	3.75 m each	undivided	1.3 m	-	4 m -
Alkali Road	Secondary	North-south	20 m	3.65 m each	Two-way two-lane	1.0 m	1.3 m	- 1.0 m
Sokoto Road	Small	East-west	13.6 m	3.0 m each	undivided	3.0 m	-	- -
More Land Kukuwa Street	Small	North-south	13.6 m	3.5 m each	undivided	1.8 m	1.0 m	- -
Club Road	Small	North-south	10.6 m	3.5 m each	undivided	1.3 m	1.0 m	- -
Tafawa Balewa Road	Secondary	North-south	20.8 m	3.6 m each	undivided	1.5 m	-	4.0 m -
Kashim Ibrahim Road	Secondary	West-east	21 m	3.65 m each	Two-way two-lane	1.3 m	1.4 m	2.6 m 1.0 m

Adjacent to the site and the current intersection with the greatest impact of vehicle access in the site is the intersection of Mohammed Buhari Road to Independence way Road, and the T-junction of Racecourse Road to Alkhali Road. The intersection of Mohammed Buhari Road and Independence way Road is a two-phase intersection controlled by traffic road safety.

Figure 4: (a) Road network planning and major intersection; (b) A view of Muhammed Buhari way Road and Independence way intersection

Figure 4(a) shows the road network planning and major intersection and Figure 4(b) shows the pictorial representation of Muhammed Buhari way Road and Independence way Road intersection. The signal timings for the mentioned intersection is shown in Table 5, while the technical standard for the same is presented in Table 6.

Table 5: Signal timings for the Muhammed Buhari way Road and Independence way intersection

Signal timing	Phase 1	Phase 2
South-North	Go straight + turn left	
East-West		Go straight + turn right
Green time (seconds)	25	23

2.4. Major Findings

It is concluded from the current survey of the public transport facilities around the project area that the bus stops in Nigeria are not well organized, there are no fix stations, and it is hard to carry out these survey. There is currently no rail transit line within the study area, but Nigeria is still a developing country, and in future, it may be available. At the intersection between Independence way Road and Muhammad Buhari way Road, pedestrians cross the intersection at the pedestrian zebra crossing, but no pedestrian signal light is set. There are no public bicycles in Nigeria which makes it hard to carry out this survey.

Table 6: Technical standard for the intersection at Muhammad Buhari way Road and Independence way

Import road name	Lane function	Number of lanes
Southbound	Left, Through and right	1
Northbound	Left, Through and right	1
Eastbound	Left, Through and right	1
Westbound	Left, Through and right	1

3. Results

3.1. Peak hour traffic volume

The collection of data for peak hour traffic volume is conducted following the Institution of Highways & Transportation Guidelines for Traffic Impact Assessment [M]. (1994). IHT specified peak hour in the morning between 1100 hrs. to 1200 hrs. This time is the peak time for mall developments. The traffic volume of the main roads and intersections are measured by recording video method for 15minutes. From the recorded video, the traffic volume is counted, and the data processing of traffic volume at sections and intersections is carried out

The pinnacle hour volume is only the whole of the volumes of the four 15 minutes inside the pinnacle hour. The pinnacle hour factor (PHF) is found by dividing the pinnacle hour volume by four times the pinnacle 15 minutes volume. $PHF = \text{Hourly Average Volume} / \text{Peak Rate of Flow if 15-min periods are utilized}$, the PHF might be processed as: $PHF = V / (4 \times V_{15})$. Where, PHF=Peak-Hour Factor, V=hourly volume (vph) and V_{15} =volume during the pinnacle 15 min of the pinnacle hour (veh/15 min). After entering the measured traffic volume data, it is necessary to convert the measured vehicle data into equivalent car data according to China's code for urban road traffic planning and design [20]. Table 7 presents the calculated peak hour traffic volume of motor vehicles on each road section around the project site.

Table 7: Calculated peak hour traffic volume of motor vehicles on each road section around the project site.

Road name	East to West (South to North)	West to East (North to South)
Moreland kukuwa street	256	280
Independence way Road	952	1276
Mohammed Buhari way Road	1132	884
Alimi Road	40	56
Sokoto Road	480	366
Race courseRoad	128	44
Club Road	240	210
Tafawa balewa Road	400	348
Kashim Ibrahim Road	956	1030
Alkhali Road	332	280
Race courseRoad 2	67	50

Figure 5 shows the current peak hour vehicle flow chart around the project site and Figure 6 presents the current peak hour background traffic service level map.

Figure 5: Current peak hour vehicle flow chart around the project site

The peak hour service level of motor vehicles in each road section of the study area is described in Table 8. It should be noted that the road level of service is divided into six levels: 0-0.4 for A, 0.4-0.6 for B, 0.6-0.75 for C, 0.75-0.9 for D, 0.9-1 for E, and > 1 for F.

Table 8: Peak hour level of service of motor vehicles in each road section of the study area

Road name	One-way capacity (pcu/h)	saturation		Service Level	
		East to west (South to North)	West to east (North to South)	East to west (South to North)	West to east (North to South)
Moreland kukuwa street	500	0.51	0.56	B	B
Independence way Road	2000	0.47	0.63	B	C
Mohammed buhari way Road	1600	0.71	0.55	C	B
Alimi Road	500	0.08	0.11	A	A
Sokoto Road	500	0.96	0.46	F	D
Race course Road	800	0.05	0.39	A	A
Club Road	500	0.48	0.42	B	B
Tafawa balewa Road	800	0.50	0.43	B	B
Kashim Ibrahim Road	1600	0.59	0.64	B	C
Alkhali Road	1600	0.20	0.17	A	A
Race course Road 2	800	0.08	0.06	A	A

Figure 6: Current peak hour background traffic level of service map

Table 9 presents the peak hour traffic volume of motor vehicles at the intersection of Muhammad Buhari way Road and Independence way Road.

Table 9: Peak hour traffic volume of motor vehicles at the intersection of Muhammad Buhari way Road and Independence way Road

Import road name	Lane name	Motor vehicle flow (pcu/h)
South import	Left, Through and right	420
North import	Left, Through and right	420
East imports	Left, Through and right	540
West import	Left, Through and right	420
total		1800

Calculation of signal timing and capacity at the same intersection is presented in Table 10. The level of service for the same intersection is presented in Table 11.

Table 10: Calculation of signal timing and capacity at the intersection of Muhammad Buhari way Road and Independence way Road

Signal timing	Phase 1	Phase 2
North and south	Go straight + turn left	
East and west		Go straight + turn left
Green time	25	23
Green letter ratio	0.46	0.43
Single lane capacity (pcu/h)	625	703
Road capacity (pcu/h)	1350	1650

Table 11: Level of service for the intersection between the Muhammed Buhari way Road and Independence way Road

Import road name	Lane function	Number of lanes	Equivalent volume flow	One-lane capacity	Saturation	Service Level
South import	Turn left	1	120	1059	0.11	A
	straight	1	660	1059	0.21	A
	Turn right	1	60	1000	0.06	A
North import	Turn left	1	120	1059	0.11	A

The traffic volume of roads and intersections within the study area has the following results:

- Sokoto Road traffic is high due to people using it as a shortcut to the market
- Racecourse Road 1 and 2 traffic is very low due to the completion of road construction;
- Main traffic flow within the evaluation scope is undertaken by Sokoto Road, Independence way Road, Mohammed Buhari way Road, the level of service of the other road section is moderate.
- In the existing roads within the evaluation scope, the construction level of secondary roads is higher, and the connectivity of branch roads needs to be strengthened.
- The overall road network within the evaluation scope is not perfect enough to play the role of traffic diversion.
- Due to a large number of development land and roads inside the scope of study, the motor vehicle traffic volume of main roads and intersections is large.

3.2. Proposed Travel demand forecast in Nigeria

TransCAD is a new traffic forecasting software that is a multi-mode balanced traffic planning system, widely used by transportation planners in China, Canada, the United States, and Europe. The forecasting model consists of the following components: traffic and road network systems, modes of transport, and flow-delay functions. The traffic planning model defines four modes of transportation: cars, other motor vehicles, buses, and other modes of travel. The flow delay function is a mathematical expression used to calculate the transit time of a vehicle on a road segment. Combined with the actual situation of the road traffic on the site, this traffic impact analysis considers two kinds of delays: the delay of the motor vehicle on the road section; and the delay of the motor vehicle at the intersection. The general steps for the process of traffic flow prediction simulation consist of four processes. These processes are trip generation, mode split, trip distribution, and trip assignment.

The amount of trip production and attraction of the traffic development depends on the land-use situation, population density and social and economic development of the land. This traffic impact analysis mainly considers the nature of land use as the point of production and attraction of traffic. Considering the location factors of this development project and the characteristics of passenger flow of different development types, this paper uses different passenger flow forecasting methods compatible with malls, which is the trip rates yet to be developed in Nigeria. The peak hour passenger flow attraction is calculated by multiplying the total number of shops' sunrise times by the morning peak hour travel coefficient. The pedestrian/100m² construction area is used as the peak hour passenger flow attraction rate unit. Regression models are worked to associate 15 minutes trip attractions and physical highlights (gross floor space, number of stores, accessibility of parking, accessibility of eatery, and so forth.) of the malls. In the regression model, 15 min trip attractions are taken as a dependent variable, and physical highlights are taken as independent variables. Information from the field overviews fill in as contributions to the advancement of regression models. These models are utilized in determining proper trip production and trip attraction dependent on an appropriate independent variables depicting trip generation attributes. Illustrative measurements are likewise created by the field information, yielding most extreme, least, and normal outing rates alongside standard deviations and other relevant data with respect to the variety of rates. Reasonable and objective transportation mode split prediction can provide scientific decision support for optimizing the future transportation mode structure of the city and can grasp the traffic loads that may be generated by the future city, more realistically. In determining the division of transportation mode in the planning year, it is done largely by the overall development goals of the city and the transportation development strategy.

Mode split survey is the characteristics of travel patterns of customers, employees and visitors in the region need to be analysed, and the travel modes of future years are predicted. During peak hours, the mode of travel of the mall is mainly the way of travel of the commuters. According to the proportion of the annual travel mode of the evaluation, the amount of attraction, and the amount of different formats during the peak hour, the passenger flow rate of the peak hour evaluation year needs to be obtained. Currently, Nigeria has no rail transit system so far and the percentage of rail transit can be neglected when analysing TIA in Nigeria and also according to [17]. The rapid growth of the private vehicle fleet, combined with reliance on minibuses for commercial vehicles, private car owners and motorcycles [9] increased the percentage of cars use in Nigeria.

The number of passengers carrying out motor vehicles at different peaks has personality characteristics. Dividing the passenger flow by the average passenger load and multiplying by the vehicle conversion factor, one can get the peak hour standard traffic flow.

Trip distribution prediction refers to the number of traffic cells obtained in the trip generation prediction, and the amount of attraction is converted into the space entanglement between the traffic cells, that is, the O-D matrix. Therefore, the travel distribution model is a spatial joint function model. The site development format is mainly commercial, and the distribution of new traffic demand of the site is determined according to the location of the site and the service hinterland. The road network in 2022 is determined according to the current situation of the construction of the road network Traffic distribution.

Trip assignment model uses the fixed demand equilibrium allocation model in TransCAD software to distribute traffic to the OD matrix of the late peak. In this type of distribution model, the travel OD

matrix $T_{(i,j)}$ is fixed during the distribution process. The relevant forecast drawings for new traffic flow and link saturation of the motor vehicle network in the near-term and long-term peak hours can be obtained from TransCAD software.

The background traffic volume of the road within the study area consists of the inherent traffic volume of the relevant roads and the new traffic volume of other land parcels except for the site. The project is situated in the peripheral area of Kaduna state, and there are several developments within and around the study area. Therefore, the annual average growth rate method is used to combine the traffic volume of the surrounding plots to predict the background traffic volume of the roads around the site. The background traffic volume of the trunk road adopts an average annual growth rate of about 1-3%, and the branch road adopts an average annual growth rate of about 3-5%. The study proposes using the economic status of Kaduna city at a percentage of 3.3% to the background traffic forecast.

Table 12: Current status of the major roads in the study area and background traffic volume of the peak hour section of the target year

Road name	Current status of motor vehicle traffic		Evaluation of annual background motor vehicle flow	
	East to the west (South to North)	West to the east (North to South)	East to the west (South to North)	West to the east (North to South)
Moreland kukuwa street	256	280	281	307
Independence way Road	952	1276	1046	1402
Mohammed Buhari way Road	1132	884	1244	971
Alimi Road	40	56	43	61
Sokoto Road	480	366	527	402
Racecourse Road	128	44	140	48
Club Road	240	210	263	230
Tafawa balewa Road	400	348	439	382
Kashim Ibrahim Road	956	1030	1050	1131
Alkhali Road	332	280	364	307
Racecourse Road 2	67	50	73	54

The current status of the major roads in the study area and background traffic volume of the peak hour section of the target year is shown in Table 12. The peak hour level of service of motor vehicles of the target year in each road section of the study area is presented in Table 13.

Table 13: Peak hour level of service of motor vehicles of the target year in each road section of the study area

Road name	One-way capacity (pcu/h)	Saturation		Service Level	
		East to west (South to North)	West to east (North to South)	East to west (South to North)	West to east (North to South)
Moreland kukuwa street	500	0.56	0.61	B	C
Independence way Road	2000	0.52	0.70	B	C
Mohammed buhari way Road	1600	0.77	0.60	D	C
Alimi Road	500	0.08	0.12	A	A
Sokoto Road	500	1.05	0.80	F	D
Racecourse Road	800	0.17	0.06	A	A
Club Road	500	0.52	0.46	B	B
Tafawa balewa Road	800	0.54	0.47	B	B
Kashim Ibrahim Road	1600	0.65	0.70	C	C
Alkhali Road	1600	0.22	0.19	A	A
Racecourse Road 2	800	0.09	0.06	A	A

The construction of the parking lot is mainly based on the nature and scale of each construction project and the distribution in the city, and the parking spaces for motor vehicles and non-motor vehicles are allocated according to the relevant regulations of Kaduna City which are yet to be developed. The site needs to be equipped with non-motor vehicle parking spaces

Public transportation priority is the right development direction of urban transportation in Kaduna, and the site residents have a certain proportion of public transportation. The public construction facilities in the site mainly serve the commercial area of the community and surrounding areas, and there is no need for rail transit shortly. The evaluation of the annual public transport travel needs to be developed.

4. Discussions

In the existing roads within the evaluation scope, the construction level of the secondary roads is significant, and the level of connectivity of the branch roads needs massive improvement. The overall road network within the evaluation scope is not enough to play the role of traffic diversion. Due to a large number of land development and roads within the project area, the motor vehicle traffic volume of main roads and intersections is large.

It is concluded, after assigning forecasted traffic counts to background traffic that the degree of attained services needs improvement. One way to improve the below average level of service of the current road network is expanding the road width around the project site. Particularly, the width of Sokoto Road needs to be expanded because the service level of the same is F.

5. Conclusion

Development of projects imposes additional traffic on the existing traffic and adjoining road infrastructure. The volume of the additional traffic depends on various factors like the intended use of the project and development and construction intensity. This additional traffic causes delays and inconvenience to commuters and incurs additional costs to make alternatives, which is not beneficial for both the policymakers and the general public. The effect of the additional traffic on the existing traffic facilities is directly proportional to the extent and complexity of the project development. For larger and more complex projects, the effects of additional traffic on local traffic is more prominent. Nigeria is a developing country with a high population, and the country is already facing traffic flow and management issues owing to rate of its urban expansion, especially in major cities that attract investment for mega projects. Proposed development projects in Nigeria must allow TIA to forecast and fix its impact on traffic and transportation.

1. The model that fits adequately to the traffic congestion issues of Nigeria is the Chinese TIA because of the relevance in high population, rapid urbanization, GDP growth rate, and increase in the number of personal vehicles.
2. By implementing the Chinese TIA in Nigeria, the improvements according to the traffic volume in the current road operations are proposed. The current capacity of the traffic system is assessed, which is incapable of accommodating the increase in the traffic due to the construction of the project.
3. The adoption of Chinese TIA in Nigeria is first of its kind and includes the introduction of the same in Nigeria. Only a few aspects have been introduced. Additional work needs to be done in forecasting the travel demand, to plan and execute mitigation measures, estimating annual public transport and parking demand, evaluating mode split and traffic distribution and assignment.

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Dedication

I would like to dedicate my research to my loving parents.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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